

DELIVERABLE

DL.3.2.6: REPORT ON THE SCIENTIFIC STUDY IN COMMERCIAL SLAUGHTERHOUSES OF TURKEYS WITH WATERBATH

Table of contents

1. Introduction.....	3
2. Methods	3
2.1. Selection of slaughterhouses and animals	3
2.2. Description of the slaughterhouses and waterbath stunning systems.....	3
2.3. Assessment of the consciousness	4
2.3.1 Observers.....	4
2.3.2 Sample assessment	5
2.3.3. Indicators for the assessment	6
2.4. Statistical analysis.....	7
2.4.1. Inter-observer repeatability of ABIs	7
2.4.2. Correlation among ABIs	7
2.4.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning efficiency.....	7
3. Results.....	8
3.1. Inter-observer repeatability of the ABIs	8
3.1.1. Before bleeding	8
3.1.2. During bleeding.....	12
3.2. Correlation among ABIs	15
3.2.1. Before bleeding	15
3.2.2. During bleeding.....	15
3.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning effectiveness	16
3.3.1. Before bleeding	16
3.3.2. During bleeding.....	18
4. Discussion.....	19
4.1. Inter-observer repeatability of the ABIs	19
4.2. Correlation among ABIs	20
4.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning efficiency.....	21
5. Conclusions and recommendations.....	21
6. References	22

1. Introduction

Avoiding pain, fear and distress through a rapid induction of unconsciousness and death during slaughter is the main objective to be achieved by the stunning in turkeys. An unconscious animal is insensitive to stimulations from the environment as the brain is no longer capable of dealing with sensory information (Terlouw *et al.*, 2016a). However, in waterbath stunning (WBS), although with the electrical current parameters set up by the regulation, not all birds are successfully rendered unconscious and some of them may be ineffective stun or recover consciousness before death. For this reason, it is a legal requirement to check that birds are unconscious from the exit of the waterbath until death occur through bleeding and exsanguination. EFSA (2013) provides a list of animal-based indicators (ABIs) in poultry to evaluate the state of consciousness including the level of sensitivity, specificity and feasibility. However, the prevalence, the inter-observer repeatability and the correlation among these ABIs has been assessed by EURCAW-Poultry-SFA in broilers but not in turkeys yet.

This study is aimed at investigating the pertinence of different ABIs for the assessment of turkey's state of consciousness after WBS before and during bleeding. The inter-observer repeatability of these indicators was studied in order to assess the repeatability of already validated ABIs that can be used for the assessment of the state of consciousness in commercial slaughterhouses. Moreover, the correlation among the outcomes of the ABIs and the effectiveness of stunning according to different combinations of waterbath electrical key parameters (frequency and current) used in different commercial slaughterhouses will be assessed.

2. Methods

2.1. Selection of slaughterhouses and animals

Eight commercial turkey slaughterhouses (SHs) equipped with WBS were selected in France and Spain. Selection of the SHs was carried together with the official veterinary services and reflect a certain diversity in terms of size of the plant, electrical key parameters, turkeys' genotypes and weight, and line speed. Each SH was assigned to a number (SH from 1 to 8).

2.2. Description of the slaughterhouses and waterbath stunning systems

Substantial variation of age, design and construction of the SHs were observed, and the main characteristics are shown in Table 1.

In all SHs, turkeys were individually hung upside down by the legs on moving shackles of the slaughter line and stunned by immersion of the head in the electrified waterbath (WB). None of them had adjustable shackles to different weight and size of the bird's legs. The height of the waterbath was adjusted according to the size of the birds to facilitate all birds an immersion up to the base of their wings. Line speed was not measured *in situ*. The values are those reported by the food business operators and the official veterinary service. A digital control panel monitored the electrical parameters applied (*i.e.*, actual total current amount passing through the WB, the voltage and the frequency) in all SHs. The automatically recorded electrical parameters were obtained from the SHs but were not measured and verified. The average values of current per animal was calculated by dividing the total current amount passing through the WB by the number of

birds simultaneously in the water. The electrical waveform was sine alternating current in all the SHs. The bleeding procedure differed among SHs. Hence, four of them did manual bleeding through bilateral section of carotids (SH-1, SH-2, SH-3, SH-4 and SH-8), two of them did manual bleeding by cutting the carotids through an oropharynx incision (SH-5 and 6) and one of them used an automatic neck cutter to section the two carotids (SH-7). Slaughter line speed ranged from 300 to 3,000 birds/h.

Table 1. Main characteristics of the eight slaughterhouses that used waterbath (WB) stunning system included in the study.

	Slaughterhouse							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Location	France	France	France	Spain	Spain	Spain	Spain	France
WB length (m)	1.9	3.0	3.6	3.6	0.8	2.1	2.6	3.4
Birds in the WB (n)	5	4	8	5	2	7	7	10
Exposure time (s)	NA	9 (♂), 7 (♀)	12 (♂), 16 (♀)	18	6	22	13	22
Line speed (birds/h)	1,000	2,100 (♂), 3,000 (♀)	1,800 (♂), 2,800 (♀)	700	300	350	1,300 (♂), 2,000 (♀)	1,860
Stun-to-stick interval (s)	8-9	6	6	29	30	23	NA	13
Bleeding method*	M	M	M	M	M	M	A	M

*Bleeding method: M (manually); A (automatically)
NA: not available

2.3. Assessment of the consciousness

2.3.1 Observers

The assessment of the stunning effectiveness was carried out by four trained observers. Each observer (Obs) was named as letter (A to D). An additional person randomly selected and identified the birds to be assessed by pointing at the bird with a laser pointer to prevent mistakes at evaluating all four observers the same selected bird. The stunning effectiveness was assessed in two different places of the slaughter line; 1) at the exit of the WB before bleeding and 2) during bleeding at approximately 6-8 s (in SH-1, SH-5, SH-6, SH-7, SH-8), 11 s (in SH-2) and 18 s (in SH-3) after severing the carotids, (Figure 1) in a representative sample of birds in each batch. The four observers assessed the bird and scored the ABIs between 3 and 6 s, depending on the slaughterhouse design and visibility. Observers assessed the ABIs independently and did not discuss or disclose their assessments during the evaluation.

Figure 1. Position of the observers (A to D) during the assessment of ABIs of the effectiveness of waterbath stunning in turkeys. The position of the lens is the position of the observers (*i.e.*, before and during bleeding) and the red segments are the observation area.

2.3.2 Sample assessment

All the batches of turkeys slaughtered during the presence of the observers in the plant were evaluated. On each batch, samples of 50-100 birds were assessed before and during bleeding. This cycle was repeated until the whole batch was slaughtered, in order to reach the biggest sample size possible.

A summary of the electrical parameters used per batch and per SH along with the characteristics of the animals in the batch and the number of assessed birds is shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Number of batches of slaughtered turkeys, sex, average body weight and age of the turkeys per batch for each slaughterhouse. The number of turkeys assessed before and during bleeding, the average electrical parameters \pm standard deviation of the waterbath are also reported.

SH	Batch	Characteristics of the birds				No. Birds assessed		Electrical parameters		
		Sex	No. Birds	BW, kg	Age, d	BB	DB	Current, mA/bird	Frequency, Hz	Voltage, V
1	1	Female	2,000	4.2	57	0	200	289 \pm 29	150	300
	2	Male	3,148	3.8	64	199	200	345 \pm 33	150	300
	3	Female	2,770	3.8	64	250	300	367 \pm 25	150	300
2	1	Male	1,820	15.9	NA	0	39	293 \pm 39	199	145 \pm 0
	2	Male	4,595	16.2	NA	187	150	319 \pm 65	199	141 \pm 2
	3	Female	2,212	7.8	NA	0	190	303 \pm 33	199	140 \pm 0
	4	Female	2,478	6.3	NA	192	68	278 \pm 46	199	140 \pm 0
3	1	Male	4,500	16.6	126	199	200	NA	199	NA
	2	Male	5,500	7.7	91	200	213	NA	199	NA
	3	Male	3,456	15.1	127	181	180	NA	199	NA
	4	Male	4,280	16.0	131	199	213	284 \pm 50	196	187 \pm 3
	5	Male	2,050	11.1	113	69	180	287 \pm 35	196	186 \pm 8
	6	Male	1,675	12.1	118	198	200	302 \pm 55	196	206 \pm 3
	7	Male	3,880	15.6	124	246	200	311 \pm 61	196	229 \pm 2
4	1	Female*	910	10.5	103	66	150	659 \pm 66	400	375 \pm 13
	2	Female*	400	7.6	105	120	58	634 \pm 49	400	360
	3	Female*	400	10.8	105	0	142	677 \pm 75	400	407 \pm 5
5	1	Female*	445	12.4	120	197	200	208 \pm 88	75	285
	2	Female*	462	12.4	122	99	148	177 \pm 94	75	285
6	1	Female	126	7.6	80	50	90	479 \pm 125	330	350
	2	Female	210	10.7	109	13	100	400 \pm 119	330	350
	3	Female	400	10.5	111	137	128	241 \pm 80	330	350
7	1	Female	2,304	7.9	88	99	200	372 \pm 26	100	330 \pm 2
	2	Female	1,992	8.5	99	217	87	408 \pm 34	100	330 \pm 3
	3	Female	2,304	7.8	88	177	123	436 \pm 47	100	330 \pm 3
	4	Female	2,304	7.7	88	164	0	388 \pm 59	100	330 \pm 3
	5	Female	1,568	7.8	88	0	32	NA	NA	NA
8	1	Male**	3,500	15.4	128	200	224	275 \pm 57	171	243 \pm 2

N° Birds: number of birds in the batch; SH: slaughterhouse; BW: body weight; BB: before bleeding; DB: during bleeding; NA: not available

*Mostly females but some males; **Mostly males but some females

2.3.3. Indicators for the assessment

The ABIs for the assessment of the state of consciousness before and during bleeding were selected based on those proposed by EFSA (2013). The selected ABIs before bleeding were tonic seizure, breathing, spontaneous blinking and vocalisations, while the selected ones during bleeding were wing flapping, breathing, spontaneous swallowing and head shaking. The description and the outcome of consciousness and unconsciousness of these ABIs is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Animal-based indicators (ABI) assessed and descriptions of the outcomes of unconsciousness and consciousness in turkeys stunned by waterbath in two different stages: before and during bleeding. Adapted from EFSA (2013).

Stage	ABI	Outcome of unconsciousness	Outcome of consciousness
Before bleeding	Tonic seizure	Bird shows general loss of muscle tone and a completely relaxed body and flaccid body, with no neck tension.	Bird shows arched and stiff neck (<i>i.e.</i> , necks appear parallel to the ground) and wings held tightly close to the body.
	Breathing	Absence of movements of the beak or abdominal muscles around the cloaca associated to cessation of breathing.	Presence of either a minimum of two movements of the beak or abdominal muscles around the cloaca associated to breathing.
	Spontaneous blinking	Bird does not open/close eyelid on its own (fast or slow) without stimulation.	Bird opens/closes eyelid on its own (fast or slow) without stimulation.
	Vocalisations	Absence of single or repeated short and loud shrieking (screaming) at high frequencies.	Single or repeated shrieking (screaming).
During bleeding	Wing flapping	Absence of flapping with both wings.	Flapping with both wings and should not be confused with rapid trembling of the entire body of the bird.
	Breathing	Absence of movements of the beak or abdominal muscles around the cloaca associated to cessation of breathing.	Either a minimum of two movements of the beak or abdominal muscles around the cloaca associated to breathing.
	Spontaneous swallowing	Absence of deglutition reflex.	Deglutition reflex triggered by water from the stunner or blood from the neck-cutting wound entering the mouth during bleeding.
	Head shaking	Bird does not shake its head from side to side.	Bird shakes its head from side to side to get rid of blood or water entering the nostrils.

The four trained observers agreed beforehand on the definition of the indicators, the methodology of assessment and the scoring to standardize the protocol when assessing the birds with these indicators.

Before the assessment of the birds, the four assessors were placed where there was the best possible visibility towards the shackled birds from a ventral position. However, due to divergence in the design and construction of the SHs, sometimes the birds were assessed from a dorsal position instead of ventral at the exit of the WB and during bleeding (SH-2, SH-3 and SH-5) or before but not during bleeding (SH-6) and thus, impairing the assessment of breathing by direct observation of abdominal muscles around the cloaca rhythmic movements. Data were recorded as binomial as 0 if the outcome of unconsciousness was observed and 1 when an outcome of consciousness was observed. The presence of at least one outcome of consciousness may indicate the bird is conscious or regaining consciousness after WBS and therefore of an ineffective stunning or a long stun-to-stick interval (*i.e.*, time from stunning to the start of bleeding).

2.4. Statistical analysis

Data pre-processing, statistical analyses and plots were performed using R software v.4.1.0. (R Core Team, 2021). First, birds that were not assessed by all four observers were filtered out to ensure that all observations were directly comparable. For all the statistical analyses, significance was declared at $P < 0.05$.

2.4.1. Inter-observer repeatability of ABIs

The overall level of agreement between observers for each ABI were determined and expressed by the crude proportion of agreement (PoA) and the Fleiss' kappa using the "irr" package of R software (Gamer *et al.*, 2019). The PoA can be misleading as it does not take into account the scores that the observers assign due to chance. Fleiss's Kappa overcomes this issue as it provides an inter-observer agreement measure between two or more observers when the variable assessed is on binomial or categorical scale. It expresses the degree to which the observed proportion of agreement among observers exceeds what would be expected if all observers made their ratings completely randomly. Kappa can range from -1 to $+1$, where 0 indicates the amount of agreement that can be expected from random chance, and 1 represents perfect agreement between the observers (McHugh, 2012). Kappa is a standardized value and thus is interpreted the same across multiple studies. Thus, according to Fleiss *et al.* (2003) Fleiss' kappa can be classified as "excellent" agreement beyond chance if values are greater than 0.75; "fair to good" agreement beyond chance if values between 0.40 and 0.75 and "poor" agreement beyond chance if the values are below 0.40. However, when there is an insufficient scoring variation in the evaluated indicator (*i.e.*, low prevalence of indicators of consciousness), although high agreement between observers, kappa appears close to 0.

2.4.2. Correlation among ABIs

As data did not follow a normal distribution, Spearman's rank correlation was performed to measure the association between the observed ABIs. Correlation results were displayed as heat map. Proportions among combinations of ABIs were performed as Venn diagram considering all turkeys assessed in the present study using the "eulerr" package (Larsson, 2020).

2.4.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning efficiency

Stunning inefficiency of each batch and SH was evaluated by showing the percentage of birds with at least one outcome of consciousness in any of the stages of the assessment: before and during bleeding. Chi-squared % defective test was used to determine if there were statistical differences among observers between the expected and the observed frequencies of every outcome of the indicators evaluated. If one observer differed statistically from the others at evaluating the ABIs, the mean of the proportion of the two closest evaluations or the in between value when scoring were not consistent among them were reported. Prevalence of each indicator within each batch was calculated and from this, the interval of confidence in the population (here in each batch) was calculated. Thus, 95% confidence interval of turkeys showing outcomes of consciousness was computed using the Wilson's formula from "epitools" package of R software (Aragon, 2020) in every batch assessed.

3. Results

The ABIs were assessed on a total of 3,690 turkeys before bleeding and 3,659 during bleeding from eight different SHs across France and Spain by four observers. However, not all of them could have been assessed by the four observers (for technical reason). Those not assessed by all four observers were filtered out. Thus, 3,659 turkeys remained in the dataset before bleeding and 4,218 during bleeding. The number of the birds assessed per SH as well as the number and percentage of birds assessed by the four observers is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Number of assessed animals and number and percentage of birds that were able to be assessed by the four observers according to the slaughterhouse (before and during bleeding).

Birds assessed	Slaughterhouse								All
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
<i>Before bleeding</i>									
Total number of birds assessed	450	387	1,301	187	300	200	665	200	3,690
Number of birds assessed by the four observers	449	379	1,292	187	296	200	657	200	3,659
Birds assessed by the four observers, %	99.8	97.9	99.3	100.0	98.7	100.0	98.8	100.0	99.2
<i>During bleeding</i>									
Total number of birds assessed	700	450	1,390	350	348	320	442	429	4,429
Number of birds assessed by the four observers	700	447	1,389	350	348	311	442	423	4,218
Birds assessed by the four observers, %	100.0	99.3	99.9	100.0	100.0	97.2	100.0	98.6	95.2

3.1. Inter-observer repeatability of the ABIs

3.1.1. Before bleeding

After WBS and before bleeding, four ABIs of the state consciousness were assessed: tonic seizure breathing, spontaneous blinking and vocalisation. The average prevalence of birds between batches showing outcomes of consciousness, by observer and SH is shown in Table 5. On the other hand, the overall level of agreement between the four observers for these ABIs according to the SH is shown in Table 6.

3.1.1.1. Tonic seizure

Birds with absence of tonic seizure at the exit of the waterbath was observed in all SHs. However, there was difference in its prevalence according to the SH assessed (Table 5). While SH-3 did not exceed the 17.2% in average among observers, SH-1 and SH-4 had the highest prevalence in the sample (100%). In any case, PoA was above 76% in all the SHs except for the SH-2 where it was lower (58.6%) as observer C scored 1.6 times more birds with absence of tonic seizure compared with the other observers ($P < 0.001$). The prevalence of absence of tonic seizure strongly differed between SHs and thus, so the κ and its interpretation where SH-2 was interpreted as “poor agreement”; SH-3, SH-5 and SH-6 as “fair to good” and SH-7 and SH-8 as “excellent”. Fleiss’ kappa could not be computed neither in SH-1 nor SH-4 due to absence of scoring variation as all turkeys assessed showed absence of tonic seizure (Table 6).

Table 5. Percentage of the outcomes of the animal-based indicators for the state of consciousness in turkeys before bleeding (TS: tonic seizure; BR: breathing; SB: spontaneous blinking; VC: vocalisation) according to the observer (A to D) and slaughterhouses (SH) assessed.

SH	Birds, n	Absence of TS, %						Presence of BR, %						Presence of SB, %						Presence of VC, %					
		A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value
1	449	100	100	100	100	100	1.000	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.6	0.965	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.05	0.381	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
2	379	15.8a	16.9a	26.9b	19.0ab	17.2	<0.001	0.0	0.3	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.299	1.6b	0.3a	0.0a	0.0a	0.10	0.003	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
3	1,292	94.4a	98.3b	97.6b	98.1b	99.0	<0.001	1.0	1.4	2.1	1.4	1.5	0.142	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.572	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
4	186	100	100	100	100	100	1.000	0.0	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.1	0.391	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	0.13	0.391	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
5	296	91.2	91.6	94.6	92.9	92.6	0.385	7.8	7.4	11.1	8.1	8.6	0.347	0.3ab	1.7b	0.3ab	0.0a	0.20	0.037	0.3	0.0	0.7	0.0	0.3	0.299
6	200	98.5	99.5	98	98.5	98.5	0.626	0.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	0.2	0.111	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.00	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
7	657	53.4	51.6	57.1	54.9	54.2	0.232	0.6	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.880	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.2	0.20	0.801	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
8	200	98.5	98.5	98.0	97.5	98.1	0.862	1.5	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.953	0.0	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.570	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
All	3,459	80.1a	81.3ab	83.2ab	82.1b	82.3	<0.0001	1.2a	1.3a	2.0b	1.4a	1.4	0.029	0.3ab	0.3b	0.1a	0.1a	0.2	0.011	0.03	0.0	0.05	0.0	0.03	0.300

a–b = Values with different superscripts within the same row differ among observers by chance ($P < 0.05$).

n: number of birds

Table 6. Inter-observer proportion of agreement (PoA), 95% confidence interval (CI), Fleiss' kappa coefficient (κ) and interpretation, standard error (SE) of the animal-based indicators for the state of consciousness before bleeding in turkeys according to the slaughterhouse assessed.

Item	Slaughterhouse								All
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
<i>Tonic seizure</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.3 – 100)	58.6 (53.4 – 63.6)	93.8 (92.4 – 95.1)	100 (98.4 – 100)	92.2 (89.9 – 94.5)	97.5 (94.3 – 99.2)	76.7 (73.3 – 79.9)	96.0 (92.3 – 98.3)	88.4 (87.3 – 89.4)
κ (SE)	*	0.28 (0.02)	0.42 (0.01)	*	0.71 (0.02)	0.48 (0.03)	0.75 (0.02)	0.43 (0.03)	0.79 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	Poor	Fair to good	*	Fair to good	Fair to good	Excellent	Fair to good	Excellent
P-value	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
<i>Breathing</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	99.8 (99.3 – 100)	99.2 (97.7 – 99.8)	98.4 (97.5 – 99.0)	99.5 (97.1 – 100)	93.6 (90.2 – 96.1)	99.0 (96.4 – 99.9)	99.7 (98.9 – 100)	98.5 (95.7 – 99.7)	98.6 (98.1 – 98.9)
κ (SE)	0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	0.72 (0.01)	0.00 (0.03)	0.77 (0.02)	0.00 (0.03)	0.78 (0.02)	0.66 (0.03)	0.75 (0.01)
κ interpretation	Poor	Poor	Fair to good	Poor	Excellent	Poor	Excellent	Fair to good	Excellent
P-value	0.511	0.538	<0.0001	0.518	<0.0001	0.535	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
<i>Spontaneous blinking</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	99.8 (99.8 – 100)	98.2 (96.2 – 99.3)	99.7 (99.2 – 100)	99.5 (97.1 – 100)	97.6 (95.2 – 99.0)	100.0 (97.5 – 100)	99.9 (99.1 – 100)	99.0 (96.4 – 99.9)	99.4 (99.1 – 99.6)
κ (SE)	0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.01)	0.00 (0.03)	0.00 (0.02)	*	0.67 (0.02)	0.50 (0.03)	0.15 (0.01)
κ interpretation	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	*	Fair to good	Fair to good	Poor
P-value	0.511	0.588	0.527	0.518	0.599	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
<i>Vocalisation</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.3 – 100)	100 (99.2 – 100)	100.0 (99.8 – 100)	100 (98.4 – 100)	99.0 (97.1 – 99.8)	100 (98.5 – 100)	100 (99.6 – 100)	100 (98.5 – 100)	99.9 (99.7 – 100)
κ (SE)	*	*	*	*	0.00 (0.02)	*	*	*	0.00 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	*	*	*	Poor	*	*	*	Poor
P-value	*	*	*	*	0.543	*	*	*	0.512

* Insufficient scoring variation to calculate kappa coefficients (all indicator scores were 0). Kappa interpretation: ≥ 0.75 'excellent', 0.40–0.74 'fair to good', and < 0.40 'poor' agreement (Fleiss *et al.*, 2003).

Considering the data from the total of birds assessed in the present study ($n=3,690$), the 82.3% of birds showed absence of tonic seizure (Table 5) and the PoA among observers was 88.4% and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was statistically significant and interpreted as "excellent" ($\kappa = 0.79$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 6).

3.1.1.2. Breathing

Birds breathing was observed in all SHs assessed. The highest prevalence of breathing in a sample was found in SH-5 with an average of 8.5% (Table 5). The PoA was above 98.4% in all SHs (Table 6) and there was no divergence on rating among observers in any SH ($P > 0.05$) (Table 6). However, there was divergence of κ linked to the different degree of prevalence of breathing among SHs (Table 5).

Taking all birds from the SHs assessed into consideration, divergence at scoring was found since observer C scored 1.4 times more birds with presence of breathing compared with the other observers ($P < 0.05$). Thus, the calculated average with the closest outcomes for presence of breathing was 1.4% of birds (Table 5). The PoA among observers was high (98.6%) and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was statistically significant and interpreted as "excellent" ($\kappa = 0.75$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 6).

3.1.1.3. Spontaneous blinking

Birds showing spontaneous blinking were observed in all SHs except SH-6 (Table 6). However, the higher prevalence in a sample was found at SH-8 with an average of 0.5% of the turkeys (Table 5). The PoA was above 97.6% in all SH (Table 6) but there was divergence on rating among observers at SH-2 where observer A detected presence of spontaneous blinking in 6 out of 349 turkeys whereas observer B only observed 1 while observers C and D none of them ($P < 0.01$) as shown in Table 5. Moreover, there was divergence of κ and in most of the SH (SH-1, SH-2, SH-3, SH-4 and SH-5) was close to 0 showing that the prevalence of spontaneous blinking is low and when present, there was not always consensus among observers. However, κ was "fair to good" in SH-7 and SH-8 because when present, the observers at certain degree agreed (Table 6).

When considering all turkeys assessed before bleeding, lack of consistency at scoring was also found since observer A and B scored 3 times more birds with presence of spontaneous blinking compared with the observers C and D ($P < 0.05$). Therefore, the calculated average was 0.2% (Table 5). The PoA among observers was 99.4% and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was statistically significant but interpreted as "poor" agreement ($\kappa = 0.10$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 6).

3.1.1.4. Vocalisation

Vocalisation was heard only in SH-5 but if it happened not all the observers agreed (Table 5). Thus, among all ABIs assessed before bleeding, vocalisation was the one with the highest PoA (above 99.0%) and there was no divergence on rating among observers ($P > 0.05$) in any of the SHs assessed.

Taking all birds assessed in this study into consideration, detection of vocalisation was extremely low (0.04%; Table 6). Hence, the PoA among observers was 99.9% but the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was not statistically significant ($\kappa = 0.00$; $P = 0.512$; Table 6).

3.1.2. During bleeding

Four ABIs were evaluated during bleeding: wing flapping, breathing, spontaneous swallowing and head shaking. The prevalence of birds showing outcomes of consciousness, by observer and SH is shown in Table 7 and the overall level of agreement between the four observers according to the SH is shown in Table 8.

3.1.2.1. Wing flapping

Birds with presence of wing flapping were observed in all SHs except for the SH-1 and the highest prevalence was found in SH-2 (5.1% turkeys in average). In addition, there was uniformity on rating among observers in all the different SHs assessed ($P > 0.05$; Table 7). The PoA among observers was above 94.9% in all SHs assessed (Table 8). Fleiss' kappa could not be computed neither in SH-1 nor SH-7 as the PoA was 100% whereas in the rest of SHs, kappa was interpreted as "excellent" in most of the SHs assessed (Table 8).

Taking all birds from the SHs assessed into consideration, the prevalence was 2.3% and the detection of wing flapping did not differ statistically among evaluators ($P > 0.05$; Table 7). Furthermore, the PoA among observers was high (98.4%) and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was statistically significant and interpreted as "excellent" agreement among observers ($\kappa = 0.79$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 8).

3.1.2.2. Breathing

Birds with presence of breathing during bleeding were observed in all SHs assessed except in SH-1. There was no divergence on scoring presence of breathing among observers in any SH assessed ($P > 0.05$) and highest prevalence occurred in SH-6 (8.8%), followed by SH-4 (6.7%), SH-2 (5.0%), SH-5 (1.9%), SH-7 (1.1%), SH-3 (0.4%) and SH-8 (0.4%) as shown in Table 7. The PoA among observers was above 95% in all SHs assessed (Table 8). Fleiss' kappa could not be computed in SH-1 as no bird assessed breathed during bleeding, but this outcome of consciousness offered kappa values interpreted from "fair to good" to "excellent" (Table 8).

Considering the data from all SH, the mean prevalence was 2.3% and the detection of breathing did not differ statistically among evaluators ($P > 0.05$; Table 7). Moreover, the average PoA was 98.6% and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was statistically significant and interpreted as "excellent" agreement among observers ($\kappa = 0.85$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 8).

3.1.2.3. Spontaneous swallowing

Spontaneous swallowing was observed only in SH-2 in one animal and only by one of the four observers. Therefore, there was no divergence at scoring spontaneous swallowing among observers ($P > 0.05$; Table 7). For this reason, in SH-2 the PoA was 99.8% but the Fleiss' kappa interpretation was classified as "poor" and not statistically significant ($\kappa = 0.00$; $P > 0.05$). In the other SH assessed, PoA was 100% and the Fleiss' kappa could not be computed due to absence of birds showing this outcome of consciousness (Table 8).

When considering all the birds assessed, the prevalence of spontaneous swallowing was 0.0% (Table 8), the PoA was very high (99.9%), but the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was not statistically significant and classified as "poor" agreement among observers ($\kappa = 0.00$; $P = 0.504$; Table 8).

3.1.2.4. Head shaking

Birds showing head shaking were observed in all SHs assessed except in SH-1 and SH-8. There was no divergence on scoring presence of head shaking among observers in any SH assessed ($P > 0.05$) and the

Table 7. Percentage of the outcomes of the animal-based indicators for the state of consciousness in waterbath stunned turkeys during bleeding (WF: wing flapping; BR: breathing; SB: spontaneous swallowing; HS: head shaking) according to the observer (A to D) and the slaughterhouses assessed (SH).

SH	Birds, n	Absence of WF, %						Presence of BR, %						Presence of SS, %						Presence of HS %					
		A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value	A	B	C	D	Mean	P-value
1	700	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
2	447	5.4	5.1	4.7	4.9	5.0	0.972	6.3	4.9	4.9	3.8	5.0	0.412	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.391	0.9	0.9	1.6	0.7	1.0	0.568
3	1,389	3.4	2.5	3.1	2.4	2.9	0.380	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.682	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.1	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.188
4	350	3.7	3.7	3.4	3.1	2.6	0.972	6.9	6.9	6.9	6.3	6.7	0.987	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.3	0.9	0.3	0.0	0.4	0.282
5	348	3.7	4.0	3.7	3.4	2.8	0.984	1.7	1.7	2.3	1.7	1.9	0.925	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.1	0.391
6	318	2.2	1.3	2.2	2.2	1.5	0.777	9.1	8.5	8.8	8.8	8.8	0.994	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.391
7	442	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.4	-	1.1	1.1	1.1	0.9	1.1	0.984	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.2	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.572
8	224	1.3	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.9	0.570	0.9	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.896	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-
all	4,218	2.6	2.2	2.3	2.1	2.3	0.472	2.5	2.3	2.4	2.0	2.3	0.550	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	-	0.2	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.248

n: number of birds

Table 8. Inter-observer proportion of agreement (PoA), 95% confidence interval (CI), Fleiss' kappa coefficient (κ) and its interpretation and standard error (SE) of the animal-based indicators for the state of consciousness during bleeding according to the slaughterhouse assessed.

Item	Slaughterhouse								All
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	
<i>Wing flapping</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.6 – 100)	94.9 (82.4 – 96.7)	98.1 (97.2 – 98.7)	98.3 (96.3 – 99.4)	97.7 (95.5 – 99.0)	99.0 (97.2 – 99.8)	100 (99.3 – 100)	99.1 (97.6 – 99.7)	98.4 (98.0 – 98.7)
κ (SE)	*	0.70 (0.02)	0.81 (0.01)	0.85 (0.02)	0.84 (0.02)	0.88 (0.02)	*	0.75 (0.02)	0.80 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	Fair to good	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	*	Excellent	Excellent
P-value	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	*	<0.0001	<0.0001
<i>Breathing</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.6 – 100)	95.1 (92.6 – 96.9)	98.6 (97.8 – 99.1)	96.9 (94.5 – 98.4)	98.9 (97.1 – 99.7)	98.7 (96.7 – 99.7)	99.8 (99.8 – 100)	99.3 (97.9 – 99.9)	98.5 (98.1 – 98.9)
κ (SE)	*	0.73 (0.02)	0.54 (0.01)	0.87 (0.02)	0.82 (0.02)	0.95 (0.02)	0.95 (0.02)	0.57 (0.02)	0.82 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	Fair to good	Fair to good	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Excellent	Fair to good	Excellent
P-value	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001
<i>Spontaneous swallowing</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.6 – 100)	99.8 (98.8 – 100)	100 (99.8 – 100)	100 (99.2 – 100)	100 (99.1– 100)	100 (99.0 – 100)	100 (99.3 – 100)	100 (99.3 – 100)	99.9 (99.9 – 100)
κ (SE)	*	0.00 (0.02)	*	*	*	*	*	*	0.00 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	Poor	*	*	*	*	*	*	Poor
P-value	*	0.512	*	*	*	*	*	*	0.504
<i>Head shaking</i>									
PoA, % (95% CI)	100 (99.6 – 100)	97.8 (95.9 – 98.9)	99.6 (99.1 – 99.8)	98.6 (96.7 – 99.5)	99.7 (98.4 – 100)	99.7 (98.2 – 100)	99.8 (98.8 – 100)	100 (99.3 – 100)	99.5 (99.2 – 99.7)
κ (SE)	*	0.40 (0.02)	0.30 (0.01)	0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	0.00 (0.02)	0.33 (0.02)	*	0.29 (0.01)
κ interpretation	*	Fair to good	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	*	Poor
P-value	*	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.513	0.513	0.514	<0.0001	*	<0.0001

* Insufficient scoring variation to calculate kappa coefficients (all indicator scores were 0). Kappa interpretation: ≥ 0.75 'excellent', 0.40–0.74 'fair to good', and < 0.40 'poor' agreement (Fleiss *et al.*, 2003).

highest prevalence occurred in SH-2 (1.0%), followed by SH-4 (0.4%), and SH-3, SH-5, SH-6 and SH-7 (0.1% each) as shown in Table 7. The PoA among observers was above 97.8% in all SH assessed, the Fleiss' kappa could not be computed neither in SH-1 nor SH-8 as no bird assessed shake its head. In the rest of SH assessed this outcome of consciousness offered kappa values interpreted from "poor" in most of cases to "fair to good" (Table 8).

When taking all the birds assessed into consideration, the prevalence of head shaking was 0.2% and the scoring of breathing did not differ statistically among evaluators ($P > 0.05$; Table 7). The PoA among observers was very high (99.5%) and the Fleiss' kappa coefficient was interpreted as "poor" but statistically significant ($\kappa = 0.29$; $P < 0.0001$; Table 8).

3.2. Correlation among ABIs

3.2.1. Before bleeding

To elucidate the correlation among the outcomes of the ABIs assessed before bleeding, a contingency table was created. The proportions of birds showing outcomes of consciousness and their combinations of ABIs at the same bird is shown as Venn diagram (Figure 2A). Absence of tonic seizure was the most frequent indicator followed by presence of breathing and spontaneous blinking. Vocalization was absent in all turkeys assessed. Combinations between ABIs with outcomes of consciousness were almost non-existent at this stage. Heat map was not displayed in the report as no correlation was found among any ABI.

Figure 2. Venn diagram of the animal-based indicator of consciousness assessed in waterbath stunned turkeys A) before bleeding and B) during bleeding. Indicators of consciousness are: no TS: absence of tonic seizure; BR: presence of breathing; SB: presence of spontaneous blinking; VC: presence of vocalisation; WF: presence of wing flapping; HS: presence of head shaking; SS: presence of spontaneous swallowing. Numbers specify the total amount of turkeys showing each indicator or combinations of indicators from a total of 3,659 turkeys assessed before bleeding and 4,218 during bleeding.

3.2.2. During bleeding

The proportions of birds showing outcomes of consciousness and their combinations at individual level is shown as Venn diagram in Figure 2B. This diagram showed that presence of wing flapping was the most frequent outcome of consciousness observed followed by breathing and to a lesser extent, head shaking

whereas the spontaneous swallowing was absent. Additionally, some birds showed breathing accompanied primordially by wing flapping but rarely by head shaking.

Unlike the before bleeding assessment, there was correlation among ABIs as shown as a heat map in Figure 3. All correlations were positive, but only the presence of breathing and wing flapping ($r = 0.389$) and wing flapping and head shaking ($r = 0.391$) were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Figure 3. Heat map of correlations of the outcomes of the animal-based indicators for the state of consciousness during bleeding in waterbath stunned turkeys (WF: presence of wing flapping; BR: presence of breathing; SS: presence of spontaneous swallowing; HS: presence of head shaking) found when assessing 28 batches from eight different slaughterhouses. The values in the table are Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (r) and P -values. Red crosses indicate non-significant correlations ($P > 0.05$).

3.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning effectiveness

Stunning effectiveness was analysed in relation to different combinations of electrical parameters applied to batches of different characteristics (*e.g.*, body weight). To gain some insight on relationship between combination of electrical parameters and stunning effectiveness and maintenance of the state of unconsciousness in turkeys, the prevalence of birds showing indicators of consciousness were compared. Batch 4 from SH 7 was excluded in this section as there was a prevalence of conscious birds in 1.8% of turkeys before and 9.4% of turkeys during bleeding caused by waterbath breakdown but not because of the electrical parameters in use.

3.3.1. Before bleeding

Most of the turkeys did not exhibit tonic seizure at the exit of the waterbath (2,941 out of 3,659; 80.4%) and this indicator was not correlated to other outcomes of consciousness. In these cases, tonic seizure might be previously occurred while the bird was submerged in the waterbath as it may happen in long length WB or in low line speeds or the electrical parameters in WB are set to stun-to-kill the turkeys. Thus, this indicator

has low reliability in commercial conditions, and it will not be considered as an indicator of consciousness when computing the prevalence of conscious turkeys before bleeding. Apart from breathing, the assessment of wing flapping at this stage is highly recommended (although not assessed in the present study) since some turkeys that missed the waterbath appeared wing flapping at the exit. Thus, a summary of the different electrical parameters applied and the 95% confidence interval of birds showing at least one outcome of consciousness before bleeding is summarized in Table 9.

Table 9. Number of turkeys assessed (n), average body weight (BW), electrical parameters used in the waterbath, and the mean prevalence and 95% confidence interval (CI) of turkeys showing at least one outcome of consciousness before bleeding according to the slaughterhouse (SH: 1 to 8) and batch assessed.

SH	Batch	Birds, n	Sex	BW, kg	Electrical parameters in waterbath			Birds with outcomes of consciousness	
					Current, mA/bird	Frequency, Hz	Voltage, V	Mean, %¥	95% CI
1	2	199	Male	3.8	345±33	150	300	1.5	[0.5-4.3]
1	3	250	Female	3.8	367±25	150	300	0.0	[0.0-1.5]
2	2	187	Male	16.2	319±65	199	141±2	0.7	[0.1-3.0]
2	4	192	Female	6.3	278±46	199	140±0	0.0	[0.0-1.9]
3	1	199	Male	16.6	NA	199	NA	0.8	[0.1-2.8]
3	2	200	Male	7.7	NA	199	NA	0.6	[0.1-2.8]
3	3	181	Male	15.1	NA	199	NA	1.2	[0.3-3.9]
3	4	199	Male	16.0	284±50	196	187±3	1.5	[0.5-4.3]
3	5	69	Male	11.1	287±35	196	186±8	1.4	[0.3-7.8]
3	6	198	Male	12.1	302±55	196	206±3	2.0	[0.8-5.1]
3	7	246	Male	15.6	311±61	196	229±2	2.8	[1.4-5.8]
4	1	66	Female*	10.5	659±66	400	375±13	0.0	[0.0-5.5]
4	2	120	Female*	7.6	634±49	400	360	0.4	[0.1-4.6]
5	1	197	Female*	12.4	214±88	75	285	5.8	[3.5-10.3]
5	2	99	Female*	12.4	177±94	75	285	15.9	[10.2-24.7]
6	1	50	Female	7.6	479±125	330	350	0.5	[0.0-7.1]
6	2	13	Female	10.7	400±119	330	350	0.0	[0.0-22.8]
6	3	137	Female	10.5	241±80	330	350	0.0	[0.0-2.7]
7	1	99	Female	7.9	372±26	100	330±2	0.0	[0.0-3.7]
7	2	217	Female	8.5	408±34	100	330±3	0.0	[0.0-1.7]
7	3	177	Female	7.8	436±47	100	330±3	0.0	[0.0-2.1]
8	1	200	Male**	15.4	275±57	171	243±2	1.0	[0.3-3.6]

¥: mean of the four observers

NA: not available

*Mostly females but some males; **Mostly males but some females

Highlighted in red are currents used that are not in compliance with the given frequencies according to Council Regulation 1099/2009.

The combination of electrical parameters that resulted in effective stunning was found in SH-1 (in batch 1), SH-2 (in batch 4), SH-4 (in batch 1) and in SH-6 and SH-7 (all batches assessed) as any turkey showed indicators

of consciousness. Meanwhile, SH-5 showed the highest prevalence in a sample with 5.8% of conscious birds in batch 1 and 15.9% in batch 2.

3.3.2. During bleeding

A summary of the different electrical parameters applied and the 95% confidence interval of birds showing at least one outcome of consciousness during bleeding is summarized in Table 10.

Table 10. Number of turkeys assessed (n), average body weight (BW), electrical parameters used in the waterbath, and the mean prevalence and 95% confidence interval (CI) of turkeys showing at least one outcome of consciousness during bleeding according to the slaughterhouse (SH: 1 to 8) and batch assessed.

Electrical parameters in waterbath									
SH	Batch	Birds, n	Sex	BW, kg	Current, mA/bird	Frequency, Hz	Voltage, V	Mean, %¥	95% CI
1	1	200	Female	4.2	289±29	150	300	0.0	[0.0-1.9]
1	2	200	Male	3.8	345±33	150	300	0.0	[0.0-1.9]
1	3	200	Female	3.8	367±25	150	300	0.0	[0.0-1.3]
2	1	39	Male	15.9	293±39	199	145±0	10.8	[4.1-23.6]
2	2	150	Male	16.2	319±65	199	141±2	17.6	[12.7-24.9]
2	3	190	Female	7.8	303±33	199	140±0	6.6	[4.1-11.4]
2	4	68	Female	6.3	278±46	199	140±0	2.6	[0.8-10.1]
3	1	200	Male	16.6	NA	199	NA	1.4	[0.5-4.3]
3	2	213	Male	7.7	NA	199	NA	4.3	[2.2-7.8]
3	3	180	Male	15.1	NA	199	NA	3.6	[1.9-7.8]
3	4	213	Male	16.0	284±50	196	187±3	2.5	[1.0-5.4]
3	5	180	Male	11.1	287±35	196	186±8	2.0	[1.0-5.6]
3	6	200	Male	12.1	302±55	196	206±3	8.5	[3.1-9.6]
3	7	200	Male	15.6	311±61	196	229±2	8.5	[3.1-9.6]
4	1	150	Female*	10.5	659±66	400	375±13	7.0	[4.1-12.6]
4	2	58	Female*	7.6	634±49	400	360	1.7	[0.3-9.1]
4	3	142	Female*	10.8	677±75	400	407±5	9.0	[5.4-15.0]
5	1	200	Female*	12.4	214±88	75	285	5.8	[3.5-10.2]
5	2	148	Female*	12.4	177±94	75	285	5.1	[2.8-10.3]
6	1	90	Female	7.6	479±125	330	350	8.6	[4.6-16.6]
6	2	100	Female	10.7	400±119	330	350	8.0	[4.1-15.0]
6	3	121	Female	10.5	241±80	330	350	10.4	[6.4-17.5]
7	1	200	Female	7.9	372±26	100	330±2	1.0	[0.3-3.6]
7	2	87	Female	8.5	408±34	100	330±3	0.0	[0.0-4.3]
7	3	123	Female	7.8	436±47	100	330±3	0.0	[0.0-3.0]
8	1	224	Male**	15.4	275±57	171	243±2	1.3	[0.5-3.9]

¥: mean of the four observers

NA: not available

*Mostly females but some males; **Mostly males but some females

Highlighted in red are currents used that are not in compliance with the given frequencies according to Council Regulation 1099/2009.

Effective stunning was observed in all batches assessed in SH-1 and in batch 2 and 3 in SH-7 since no turkey showed indicators of consciousness. Meanwhile, batch 1 in SH-7 kept 1% average of turkeys with outcomes of consciousness with a range from 0.3 to 3.6%.

Others that failed at preventing turkeys recovering consciousness were SH-2, SH-3 (in batch 6 and 7), SH-4 and SH-5 were resulted in more than 5% of turkeys with outcomes of consciousness.

4. Discussion

One of the aims of the study was to gain insight into the inter-observer repeatability of valid and feasible ABIs for the state of consciousness after WBS in turkeys. This study compares the assessment of four observers in 7,877 turkeys from 28 batches of eight different SHs and different key electrical parameters applied in waterbath from two main turkey producer countries in the EU-27. Even though SHs were not *per se* randomly sampled, they represent quite a diversity of equipment designs, key electrical parameters combinations, line speeds and turkey's body weight. In addition, it should be highlighted that not only observers were well trained, but they also agreed on the definition of the indicators before the assessment of the birds. The number of observers was intended to cause the minimum interference to the operators. Although there was a restriction on available space for the assessment, the observers stood next to each other assessing the same animals at the same span of time. However, it might happen that the view of each observer was slightly different according to the position and the viewing angle toward the animals.

4.1. Inter-observer repeatability of the ABIs

Data were analysed at individual turkey level and the combination of Fleiss' kappa and PoA was used to assess the inter-observer repeatability of the outcomes of some ABIs for the state of consciousness. This repeatability among observers can be interpreted as "poor" to "excellent" according to the calculated kappa value (Fleiss *et al.*, 2003). Our results show that for most of the indicators, the kappa interpretation slightly varied according to the SH assessed. It happened mainly because kappa values are strongly influenced by the prevalence, and this differed strongly among SHs (when the prevalence is low so is the kappa). The only exceptions to this were in the assessment of spontaneous blinking where kappa was interpreted as poor agreement among observers in most of the cases, whereas in vocalisations the kappa was not able to be computed in 6 out of 7 SHs due to absence of this event. These results suggest that these are cases in which the calculation of kappa does not give much information *per se*. Similarly occurs when paying attention to the PoA found. High PoA may suggest that there is a high agreement among observers. However, it may happen that the agreement is high because the outcome of the indicator is very clear to detect for all when present (*e.g.*, presence of wing flapping) or, in certain cases, because the outcome of consciousness is rarely (*e.g.*, presence of spontaneous blinking and head shaking) or hardly ever observed (*e.g.*, presence of spontaneous swallowing and vocalisations). On the other hand, the agreement is lower in the outcomes of consciousness that are more frequently observed (*e.g.*, absence of tonic seizure).

Inter-observer repeatability of some ABIs for the state of consciousness after WBS in turkeys is in general good. The most repeatable indicator before bleeding is vocalisation and spontaneous blinking, followed by breathing and tonic seizure. However, spontaneous blinking and vocalisation was artificially highly repeatable because hardly ever were observed. However, when occurred there was no consensus among the observers. When considering these results for inter observer repeatability, we recommend keeping for now tonic seizure and breathing at this stage.

During bleeding, the most repeatable indicators are spontaneous swallowing followed by head shaking, breathing and wing flapping. Nevertheless, spontaneous swallowing and head shaking were artificially highly repeatable because were observed on very few occasions. For this reason, we recommend keeping breathing and wing flapping as key ABIs during bleeding despite of being less repeatable. These ABIs are more frequent and might occur in the absence of spontaneous swallowing and head shaking. Additionally, it is proposed considering also the presence of head shaking as outcome of consciousness. Nevertheless, the absence of these ABIs does not confirm unconsciousness.

Repeatability among the four observers could be influenced by impaired visibility towards the animal because of the SH design or because when paying attention to a specific ABI, the evaluator is more prone to miss a positive outcome of another ABI. However, it is likely that higher levels of inter-observer reliability could be achieved when standardizing descriptions, training and wider testing at assessing consciousness of turkey at slaughter. Hence, better training looks to be one of the key points to improve animal welfare assessment at SH. This can be achieved through completing robust training courses consisting in theoretical lectures and video clips designed to train the assessors, and then on practical field exercises in the SH until the trainees harmonise their scoring with those of the experts (Velarde and Dalmau, 2012).

4.2. Correlation among ABIs

Based on our observations, pre-stun shocks or runt (small) animals missing the waterbath are not the main cause of non-stunned turkeys as it occurs in broilers (see deliverable 3.2.2) due to lack of contact of the head with the electrified water. Only seven out of 3,659 turkeys assessed at the exit of the waterbath was observed to miss the waterbath. However, 0.7% of the total turkeys assessed were still breathing or spontaneously blinking while body was relaxed at the exit of the waterbath indicating ineffective induction of consciousness. On the other hand, some birds did not exhibit tonic seizure and this indicator was not correlated to other outcomes of consciousness before bleeding. It may be possibly caused because tonic seizure occurred while the bird was submerged in the waterbath as it may happen in long length WBs or in low line speeds. In addition, it is known that when the electrical parameters are set to stun-to-kill the birds, the induction of cardiac arrest leads to reduced or absence of tonic seizure at the exit of the waterbath (EFSA, 2013) and it does not mean that birds are conscious. Considering these arguments and the results of our study, tonic seizure might not be as reliable as the other indicators of consciousness, since it depends on SH configuration and current delivered. This might explain why a lot of unconscious birds are not showing absence of tonic seizure after WBS.

Data on the order of re-appearance of indicators during recovery in poultry is not described in literature. Despite the importance of these indicators, in the context of slaughter, their precise relationships with other indicators of consciousness or unconsciousness are insufficiently known. The study of relationships between different ABIs of state of consciousness may benefit from analyses by correlation (Terlouw *et al.*, 2016b). Sometimes, during bleeding, more than one indicator of consciousness was observed. The most common indicators of consciousness during bleeding were wing flapping and breathing. It seems that when a turkey starts breathing is more prone to show movements as wing flapping or to a lesser extent head shaking so later in the line.

4.3. Relationship between electrical parameters and stunning efficiency

One of the objectives of the present study was to compare the effectiveness of stunning between different SHs and different key electrical parameters in waterbath. Results showed that some combinations of the electrical parameters were considered effective at inducing and maintaining the state of unconsciousness during bleeding and some did not. It should be highlighted that non-effective sub-optimal electrical parameters or equipment, the use of low voltage/current or/and the application of high frequencies and poor or lack of calibration may represent an animal welfare hazard, by not guaranteeing the unconsciousness of all animals (Smaldone *et al.*, 2021). Thus, precaution when comparing the efficiency of the electrical combinations is needed as the electrical parameters used in waterbath were obtained from the FVO and were not checked *in situ* by researchers in the present study. Additionally, other parameters varied between SHs such as turkey's body weight, electrode length, distance from head to the electrode, and wetness of shackles that also influence the effectiveness of stunning. Distance from the exit of the waterbath until neck cutting also varied between slaughterhouses so delayed bleeding may increase the prevalence of birds that recover consciousness.

It is known that low frequencies (e.g., 75Hz) are more effective at stunning and require lower current intensities (Girasole *et al.*, 2015). However, different combinations with higher frequencies can also guarantee bird's welfare at slaughtering but animal's body weight should be considered when applying these combinations. Thus, for turkeys of around 4 kg of body weight, a combination of electrical parameters that resulted in effective stunning was found in SH-1 (sine alternative current (AC), 343±41 mA/bird, 150 Hz and 300 V) where no animal was found with outcomes of consciousness except for 3 conscious turkeys out of 449 that missed the waterbath. Similarly occurred in turkeys around 8 kg of body weight where a combination that resulted in effective stunning was found in SH-7 (sine alternative current (AC), 402±50 mA/bird, 100 Hz and 330 V) where all animals were effectively stunned and none of them recovered consciousness before death. In turkeys with heavier body weights (around 15 kg), electrical parameters that were effective was found in SH-8 (sine alternative current (AC), 275±57 mA/bird, 171 Hz and 243±2 V) although few turkeys showed outcomes of consciousness both before and during bleeding. In this specific case, the ones that showed outcomes of consciousness were females within a batch of males in all cases. Females are shorter than males and missed the waterbath. Electrical combinations that strongly failed at inducing or maintaining unconsciousness were found when using higher frequencies (e.g., 330 and 400 Hz) such as in SH-6 and SH-4. However, most of the conscious turkeys found in SH-4 were males within a batch of females. It looked like the electrical parameters in use were appropriate for the females (lower body weight) but not for the males (higher body weight).

Additionally, it raises the possibility that failure in the maintenance of the equipment or poor or lack of calibration might be also responsible that the electrical parameters recorded differed from what is actually delivered in the WB. It might be the case of SH-5 where at the low frequency given (*i.e.*, 75 Hz), the high prevalence of conscious turkeys were unexpectedly high.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

Before bleeding, the recommended indicator is breathing since not only is repeatable among observers but also when present, it detects the higher percentage of truly conscious birds according to EFSA (EFSA, 2013). Apart from breathing, wing flapping is also recommended although not assessed in the present study. This is because turkeys that are ineffectively stunned appear to flap their wings. On the contrary, tonic seizure is not recommended as an indicator of unconsciousness due to low reliability in commercial conditions since it is not correlated to others before bleeding probably because tonic seizure occurred in some birds while the bird was still in the waterbath. However, presence of spontaneous blinking or vocalisation should not be neglected as indicators of consciousness and ineffective stunning. Any turkey that showed at least one

outcome of consciousness should be re-stunned with backup stunning methods without unshackling them and before being neck cut.

During bleeding, breathing and wing flapping are the recommended indicators to assess the state of consciousness during bleeding. However, head shaking should not be neglected as indicator of consciousness. Spontaneous swallowing is not recommended since its repeatability is poor and its prevalence is almost inexistent or undetectable. Similarly than before bleeding, any turkey that showed at least one of the outcomes of consciousness should be re-stunned with backup methods as soon as detected. If some turkeys of the same batch are regaining consciousness, electrical parameters should be readjusted to ensure bird's unconsciousness until death.

Repeatability among observers at detecting indicators of consciousness among observers can be increased by standardizing descriptions, robust training and wider testing at assessing consciousness of turkey at slaughter. These are key points to protect animal welfare at the time of killing.

In the turkey industry, there is a broad range of body weights at slaughter. This adds difficulty at providing recommendations on electrical parameters in turkeys since the efficiency of stunning varies according to the animals' body weight. Despite of this, some combinations of electrical parameters resulted in effective stunning in turkeys of around 4 kg of body weight (343 ± 41 mA/bird, 150 Hz and 300 V), 8 kg of body weight (402 ± 50 mA/bird, 100 Hz and 330 V) and 15 kg of body weight (275 ± 57 mA/bird, 171 Hz and 243 V).

Sexual dimorphism in turkeys should be taken into account at the time of killing. Males are heavier and taller than females and if they are not caught and crated separately on farm, then are found mixed in the slaughter line. In this sense, males found in a batch of females are more prone to be ineffectively stunned because the combination of electrical parameters might be adequate for the females (lower body weight) but not for the males. In addition, females found in a batch of males are more prone to miss the WB due to shorter stature. Therefore, better practices are needed to solve this welfare issue. Crating males separately from females on farm and then adjust both the height of the WB and the electrical parameters in use according to sex is proposed to maximise the stunning effectiveness and the welfare of turkeys at the time of killing.

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